

EFFECT OF IN-PLANE SHEAR NONLINEARITY ON BUCKLING
OPTIMIZATION OF FIBER-COMPOSITE LAMINATE SHELLS

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ABSTRACT

The buckling strength of fiber-composite laminate shells with a given material system is maximized with respect to fiber orientations using a sequential linear programming method together with a simple move-limit strategy. While a modified Riks nonlinear solution algorithm is utilized to analyze the buckling and the postbuckling behaviors of composite shells, both linear and nonlinear in-plane shear formulations are employed to form the finite-element constitutive matrix for fiber-composite laminae. Results of this optimization study using both linear and nonlinear in-plane shear formulations for simply supported composite cylindrical shells subjected to external hydrostatic compression and with different laminate layups, $[\pm\theta/90_2/0]_s$ and $[\pm\theta/90_2/0_2/90_2/\mp\theta]$, are presented.

KEYWORDS: Optimization; Buckling; Postbuckling; Shells; In-plane Shear.

1. INTRODUCTION

The buckling of shell structures encompasses a class of problems which have received extensive attention in the literature (1). However, little attention has been paid to the buckling problems of composite shells. Recently, the use of modern high modulus and high strength fiber composite materials (Fig. 1) to advanced shell structures such as submarine pressure hulls, surface ships and aircraft fuselages have been increased rapidly. In many situations buckling is an undesirable phenomenon in safe and reliable design of these advanced composite shells. Since the buckling strength of fiber composite shells heavily depends on ply orientations, the proper selection of appropriate fiber orientations for a given composite material system to achieve the maximum buckling strength of composite shells becomes a crucial problem.

Most optimization studies of composite shells up to now have been dealt with linear material properties (2,3). However, the nonlinear in-plane shear is expected to have a significant influence on the load bearing capacity of

composite laminae (4,5). In this paper the optimization for buckling resistance of fiber-composite laminate cylindrical shells with respect to fiber orientations including the nonlinear in-plane shear effect is presented. For the purpose of comparison, optimizations using the linear in-plane shear stress-strain relation are also carried out. These buckling optimization problems are solved using a sequential linear programming formulation (6) with a simple move-limit strategy (3).

To model the nonlinear in-plane shear behavior, the constitutive equations developed by Hahn and Tsai (4) are used and incorporated into the ABAQUS finite element program (7). This study uses a modified Riks nonlinear incremental algorithm (8,9) implemented in ABAQUS to calculate the buckling loads and to analyze the postbuckling behavior of composite shells. In this paper, the nonlinear buckling analysis, the constitutive matrix for a single lamina, the constitutive matrix for a composite shell section, and the sequential linear programming method are briefly discussed. Then the results of the buckling optimization for simply supported composite cylindrical shells subjected to external hydrostatic compression with different laminate layups, $[\pm\theta/90_2/0]_s$ and $[\pm\phi/90_2/0_2/90_2/\mp\theta]$, are presented. Finally, conclusions obtained from this study are given.

2. NONLINEAR BUCKLING ANALYSIS

In the finite element program ABAQUS, the nonlinear behavior of structures is modeled through an incremental updated Lagrangian formulation (10). In order to model the potential decrease in loads and displacements as the solution evolves, a modified Riks nonlinear incremental algorithm (8,9) in ABAQUS is used to construct the equilibrium solution path. In this algorithm, the nonlinear procedure is based on a motion of a given distance along the tangent line (defined by the tangent stiffness matrix) to the current solution point. Then search for an equilibrium solution in the plane, that passes through the current solution point and that is orthogonal to the same tangent line, can be carried out using an iterative algorithm.

To model bifurcation from the prebuckling path to the postbuckling path, a geometric imperfection of the composite shell is introduced by superimposing a small fraction of the lowest eigenmode, which is determined by a linearized buckling analysis, to the original nodal coordinates of the shell as follows:

$$\{I\} = \{O\} + \epsilon t \{\psi\} \quad (1)$$

where $\{I\}$ is the resulting imperfect nodal coordinates of the shell, $\{O\}$ is the original nodal coordinates of the shell, ϵ is a scaling coefficient, t is the thickness of the shell, and $\{\psi\}$ is the normalized lowest eigenmode. In this study, ϵ is taken to be 0.001 for all the nonlinear buckling analyses.

3. CONSTITUTIVE MATRIX FOR SINGLE LAMINA

For fiber-composite laminate materials, each lamina can be considered as an orthotropic layer in a plane stress condition. The traditional incremental stress-strain relations for a linear orthotropic lamina in the material coordinates (Fig. 1) can be written as

$$\Delta\{\sigma\} = [Q_1'] \Delta\{\epsilon\} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta\{\tau_i\} = [Q_2'] \Delta\{\gamma_i'\} \quad (3)$$

$$[Q_1'] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_{11}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{\nu_{12}E_{22}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{21}E_{11}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{E_{22}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{12} \end{bmatrix}, [Q_2'] = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 G_{13} & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha_2 G_{23} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where $\{\sigma\} = \{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \tau_{12}\}^T$, $\{\tau_i'\} = \{\tau_{13}, \tau_{23}\}^T$, $\{\epsilon\} = \{\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \gamma_{12}\}^T$, $\{\gamma_i'\} = \{\gamma_{13}, \gamma_{23}\}^T$. The α_1 and α_2 are shear correction factors and are taken to be 0.83 in this study.

It is known that nonlinear in-plane shear has a significant influence on the load bearing capacity of composite laminae (4,5). Based on a complementary elastic energy density formulation, Hahn and Tsai (4) developed a nonlinear in-plane strain-stress relation for a composite lamina as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_{11}} & \frac{\nu_{21}}{E_{22}} & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} & \frac{1}{E_{22}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{12}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix} + S_{6666} \tau_{12}^2 \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

In the above equation, only one constant S_{6666} is required to account for the nonlinear in-plane shear behavior of the composite lamina. By inverting and differentiating Eq. (5), an incremental in-plane stress-strain relation, which takes the in-plane shear nonlinearity into account, for the lamina can be obtained as follows:

$$[Q_1'] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_{11}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{\nu_{12}E_{22}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{21}E_{11}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{E_{22}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{\frac{1}{G_{12}} + 3S_{6666}\tau_{12}^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

4. CONSTITUTIVE MATRIX FOR COMPOSITE SHELL SECTION

The elements used in the numerical analyses are eight-node isoparametric shell elements with six degrees of freedom per node (three displacements and three rotations). The shell formulation is based on Mindlin-type displacement field assumptions which allow transverse shear deformation (11).

During a finite element analysis, the constitutive matrices of composite materials at the integration points of shell elements must be calculated before the stiffness matrices are assembled from the element level to the structural level. For fiber-composite laminate materials, the incremental constitutive equations of a lamina in the element coordinates can be written as:

$$\Delta\{\sigma\} = [Q_1] \Delta\{\varepsilon\}, \quad [Q_1] = [T_1]^T [Q'_1] [T_1] \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta\{\tau_t\} = [Q_2] \Delta\{\gamma_t\}, \quad [Q_2] = [T_2]^T [Q'_2] [T_2] \quad (8)$$

$$[T_1] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2\phi & \sin^2\phi & \sin\phi\cos\phi \\ \sin^2\phi & \cos^2\phi & -\sin\phi\cos\phi \\ -2\sin\phi\cos\phi & 2\sin\phi\cos\phi & \cos^2\phi - \sin^2\phi \end{bmatrix}, \quad [T_2] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\phi & \sin\phi \\ -\sin\phi & \cos\phi \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where $\{\sigma\} = \{\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}\}^T$, $\{\tau_t\} = \{\tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}\}^T$, $\{\varepsilon\} = \{\varepsilon_x, \varepsilon_y, \gamma_{xy}\}^T$, $\{\gamma_t\} = \{\gamma_{xz}, \gamma_{yz}\}^T$, and ϕ is measured counterclockwise from the element local x-axis to the material 1-axis. The $[Q'_1]$ matrix used in Eq. (7) may be taken from Eq. (4) if the linear in-plane shear formulation is used, or may be taken from Eq. (6) if the nonlinear in-plane shear formulation is used.

Assume $\{\varepsilon_0\} = \{\varepsilon_{x0}, \varepsilon_{y0}, \gamma_{xy0}\}^T$ and $\{\kappa\} = \{\kappa_x, \kappa_y, \kappa_{xy}\}^T$ are the in-plane strains and the curvatures at the mid-surface of the shell section. The incremental in-plane strains at a distance, z , from the mid-surface become:

$$\Delta\{\varepsilon\} = \Delta\{\varepsilon_0\} + z\Delta\{\kappa\} \quad (10)$$

If h is the total thickness of the section, the incremental stress resultants of the shell section can be defined as:

$$\Delta\{N\} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \Delta\{\sigma\} dz = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} [Q_1](\Delta\{\varepsilon_0\} + z\Delta\{\kappa\}) dz \quad (11.a)$$

$$\Delta\{M\} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} z\Delta\{\sigma\} dz = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} z[Q_1](\Delta\{\varepsilon_0\} + z\Delta\{\kappa\}) dz \quad (11.b)$$

$$\Delta\{V\} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \Delta\{\tau_t\} dz = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} [Q_2]\Delta\{\gamma_t\} dz \quad (11.c)$$

where $\{N\} = \{N_x, N_y, N_{xy}\}^T$, $\{M\} = \{M_x, M_y, M_{xy}\}^T$ and $\{V\} = \{V_x, V_y\}^T$. If there are n layers through in the layup, the incremental constitutive matrix for a composite shell section at an element integration point can be written as a summation of integrals over the n laminae in the following form:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \Delta\{N\} \\ \Delta\{M\} \\ \Delta\{V\} \end{Bmatrix} = \sum_{j=1}^n \begin{bmatrix} (z_{jt} - z_{jb})[Q_1] & \frac{1}{2}(z_{jt}^2 - z_{jb}^2)[Q_1] & [0] \\ \frac{1}{2}(z_{jt}^2 - z_{jb}^2)[Q_1] & \frac{1}{3}(z_{jt}^3 - z_{jb}^3)[Q_1] & [0] \\ [0]^T & [0]^T & (z_{jt} - z_{jb})[Q_2] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta\{\varepsilon_0\} \\ \Delta\{\kappa\} \\ \Delta\{\gamma_t\} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

where z_{jt} and z_{jb} are distances from the mid-surface of the section to the top and the bottom of the j -th layer respectively. The $[0]$ is a 3 by 2 matrix with all the coefficients equal to zero. For a general composite shell section, extensional and flexural terms are usually coupled. However, if the laminate layup is symmetric with respect to the mid-surface of the shell section, extensional and flexural terms then become uncoupled.

5. SEQUENTIAL LINEAR PROGRAMMING

A general optimization problem may be defined as the following:

$$\text{Minimize: } f(\underline{x}) \quad (13.a)$$

$$\text{Subjected to: } g_i(\underline{x}) \leq 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, r \quad (13.b)$$

$$h_j(\underline{x}) = 0, \quad j = r+1, \dots, m \quad (13.c)$$

$$p_k \leq x_k \leq q_k, \quad k = 1, \dots, n \quad (13.d)$$

where $f(\underline{x})$ is an objective function, $g_i(\underline{x})$ are inequality constraints, $h_j(\underline{x})$ are equality constraints, and $\underline{x} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}^T$ is a vector of design variables. If a optimization problem requires maximization, we simply minimize $-f(\underline{x})$.

The concept of a sequential linear programming (6,12) is that given a feasible solution $\underline{x}_0 = \{x_{01}, x_{02}, \dots, x_{0n}\}^T$ for an optimization problem, a linear programming problem may be established by expanding the nonlinear functions about \underline{x}_0 in a Taylor series, and ignoring terms of order higher than the linear ones. With this approximation, the optimization problem, Eqs. (13.a-13.d), becomes:

$$\text{Minimize: } f(\underline{x}) \approx f(\underline{x}_0) + \nabla f(\underline{x}_0)^T \delta \underline{x} \quad (14.a)$$

$$\text{Subjected to: } g_i(\underline{x}) \approx g_i(\underline{x}_0) + \nabla g_i(\underline{x}_0)^T \delta \underline{x} \leq 0 \quad (14.b)$$

$$h_j(\underline{x}) \approx h_j(\underline{x}_0) + \nabla h_j(\underline{x}_0)^T \delta \underline{x} = 0 \quad (14.c)$$

$$p_k \leq x_k \leq q_k \quad (14.d)$$

where $\delta \underline{x} = \{x_1 - x_{01}, x_2 - x_{02}, \dots, x_n - x_{0n}\}^T$. A solution for the above equations may be easily obtained by the simplex method (13). After obtaining an initial approximate solution for Eqs. (14.a-14.d), say \underline{x}_1 , we can linearize the original problem, Eqs. (13.a-13.d), at \underline{x}_1 and solve the new linear programming problem. The process is repeated until a convergent solution is obtained.

Although the procedure for a sequential linear programming is simple, difficulties may arise during the iterations. First, the optimum solution for the approximate linear problem may violate the constraint conditions of the original optimization problem. Second, in a nonlinear problem, the true optimum solution may appear between two constraint intersections. A straightforward successive linearization in such a case may leads to an oscillation of the solution between the widely separated values. Difficulties in dealing with such problems may be avoided by imposing a "move limit" on the linear approximation (6,12). The concept of a move limit is that a set of box-like admissible constraints are placed in the range of $\delta \underline{x}$. In general, the choice of a suitable move limit depends on experience and also on the results of previous steps. Once a proper move limit is chosen at the beginning of the sequential linear programming procedure, this move limit should gradually approach to zero as the iterative process continues (6,12,14).

The algorithm of a sequential linear programming with selected move limits may be summarized as follows: (1) Linearize the nonlinear objective function and associated constraints with respect to an initial guess \underline{x}_0 . (2) Impose move limits in the form of $-\underline{S} \leq (\underline{x} - \underline{x}_0) \leq \underline{R}$, where \underline{S} and \underline{R} are properly chosen positive constraints. (3) Solve the approximate linear programming problem to

obtain an initial optimum solution \underline{x}_1 . (4) Repeat the process by redefining \underline{x}_1 with \underline{x}_0 until either the subsequent solutions do not change significantly (i.e., true convergence) or the move limit approaches to zero (i.e., forced convergence).

6. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

6.1 Buckling Optimization of Composite Shell with One Design Variable In this section, a simply supported fiber-composite laminate cylindrical shell (Fig. 2) with laminate layup $[\pm\theta/90_2/0]_s$ under external hydrostatic compression is investigated. The ends of the shell are closed. Uniform pressure loads applied at two end surfaces are transferred into equivalent concentrated ring loads applied at two circular edges. The shell is composed of graphite/epoxy and typical in-plane shear stress-strain curves are shown in Fig. 3. The objective of this study is to determine the optimal fiber angle θ to maximize the buckling load p_{CR} of the shell and to compare the result of the optimization using nonlinear shear formulation with that using linear shear formulation.

Based on the sequential linear programming, in each iteration the current, linearized optimization problem becomes:

$$\text{Maximize: } p_{CR}(\theta) \approx p_{CR}(\theta_0) + (\theta - \theta_0) \left. \frac{\partial p_{CR}}{\partial \theta} \right|_{\theta = \theta_0} \quad (15.a)$$

$$\text{Subjected to: } 0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ \quad (15.b)$$

$$-r \times q \times 0.5^s \leq (\theta - \theta_0) \leq r \times q \times 0.5^s \quad (15.c)$$

where θ_0 is a solution in the current iteration. The r and q are the size and the reduction rate of the move limit. In this study, the values of r and q are selected to be 10° and $0.9^{(N-1)}$, where N is a current iteration number. To control the oscillation of the solution, a parameter 0.5^s is introduced in the move limit (3), where s is the number of oscillation of the derivative $\partial p_{CR}/\partial \theta$ that has taken place before the current iteration.

The derivative $\partial p_{CR}/\partial \theta$ in Eq. (15.a) may be approximated by using a forward finite-difference method as follows:

$$\frac{\partial p_{CR}}{\partial \theta} \approx \frac{[p_{CR}(\theta_0 + \Delta\theta) - p_{CR}(\theta_0)]}{\Delta\theta} \quad (16)$$

In order to determine the value of $\partial p_{CR}/\partial \theta$ in Eq. (16), two buckling analyses are required to compute $p_{CR}(\theta_0)$ and $p_{CR}(\theta_0 + \Delta\theta)$ in each iteration. In this study, the value of $\Delta\theta$ is selected to be 1° in most iterations.

Important numerical results obtained in the optimization study are given in Fig. 4, which shows the fiber orientation θ and the associated critical buckling pressure p_{CR} determined in each iteration. The initial values of θ are selected to be 90° for both analyses with different shear formulations. For the solution based on the nonlinear shear formulation, after eleven iterations the optimal value of θ converges to 60.3° and the optimal critical buckling pressure converges to 175.1 Mpa. For the solution based on the linear shear

formulation, after twelve iterations the optimal value of θ converges to 60.8° and the optimal critical buckling pressure converges to 176.0 Mpa.

Figure 5 shows the load-end displacement curves for the composite shell associated with the first iteration (initial guess) and the final iteration (optimal solution). It is cleared that as the solution converges from the initial guess to the optimal solution not only the critical buckling pressure of the shell is increased but also the postbuckling strength of the shell is greatly improved. Under the initial guess condition, there is a significant reduction on the critical buckling pressure and the postbuckling strength of the composite shell using the nonlinear shear formulation. However, under the optimal solution condition, the buckling and the postbuckling behaviors of the composite shell using the nonlinear shear formulation are very similar to those of the shell using the linear shear formulation.

6.2 Buckling Optimization of Composite Shell with Two Design Variables In this section, the composite laminate shell with the same geometry, end condition and loading condition as that in the previous section but with unsymmetric laminate layup $[\pm\phi/90_2/0_2/90_2/\mp\theta]$ is investigated. The objectives of this study are to find the optimal fiber orientations ϕ and θ to maximize the critical buckling pressure of the composite shell, and to examine the influence on the results of optimization due to the shear nonlinearity and the change of unsymmetric laminate layup.

Based on the sequential linear programming, in each iteration the current, linearized optimization problem becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Maximize: } P_{CR}(\phi, \theta) \approx & P_{CR}(\phi_0, \theta_0) + (\phi - \phi_0) \left. \frac{\partial P_{CR}}{\partial \phi} \right|_{\phi=\phi_0, \theta=\theta_0} \\ & + (\theta - \theta_0) \left. \frac{\partial P_{CR}}{\partial \theta} \right|_{\phi=\phi_0, \theta=\theta_0} \end{aligned} \quad (17.a)$$

$$\text{Subjected to: } 0^\circ \leq \phi \leq 90^\circ \quad (17.b)$$

$$0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ \quad (17.c)$$

$$-r_1 \times q_1 \times 0.5^{s_1} \leq (\phi - \phi_0) \leq r_1 \times q_1 \times 0.5^{s_1} \quad (17.d)$$

$$-r_2 \times q_2 \times 0.5^{s_2} \leq (\theta - \theta_0) \leq r_2 \times q_2 \times 0.5^{s_2} \quad (17.e)$$

where ϕ_0 and θ_0 are the solutions in the current iteration. The values of r_1 and r_2 (the sizes of move limits) are selected to be 10^0 . The values of q_1 and q_2 (the reduction rates of move limits) are selected to be $0.9^{(N-1)}$, where N is a current iteration number. The s_1 and s_2 are the number of oscillation of the derivatives $\partial P_{CR}/\partial \phi$ and $\partial P_{CR}/\partial \theta$. The derivative terms in Eq. (17.a) may be approximated with the following finite-difference forms:

$$\frac{\partial P_{CR}}{\partial \phi} \approx \frac{[P_{CR}(\phi_0 + \Delta\phi, \theta_0) - P_{CR}(\phi_0, \theta_0)]}{\Delta\phi} \quad (18.a)$$

$$\frac{\partial P_{CR}}{\partial \theta} \approx \frac{[P_{CR}(\phi_0, \theta_0 + \Delta\theta) - P_{CR}(\phi_0, \theta_0)]}{\Delta\theta} \quad (18.b)$$

To determine the values of $\partial p_{CR}/\partial\phi$ and $\partial p_{CR}/\partial\theta$ in in the above equations three buckling analyses are required to compute $p_{CR}(\phi_0, \theta_0)$, $p_{CR}(\phi_0 + \Delta\phi, \theta_0)$ and $p_{CR}(\phi_0, \theta_0 + \Delta\theta)$ in each iteration. The values of $\Delta\phi$ and $\Delta\theta$ are selected to be 1° in most iterations.

Important numerical results obtained in optimization study are given in Fig. 6, which shows the fiber orientations ϕ and θ , and the associated critical buckling pressure p_{CR} determined in each iteration. The initial values of ϕ and θ are selected to be 90° and 90° for both solutions using different shear formulations. For the solution based on the nonlinear shear formulation, after thirteen iterations the optimal values of ϕ and θ converge to 90° and 53.7° respectively and the optimal critical buckling pressure converges to 187.5 Mpa. For the solution based on the linear shear formulation, after twelve iterations the optimal values of ϕ and θ converge to 90° and 53.9° respectively and the optimal critical buckling pressure converges to 188.3 Mpa.

Figure 7 shows the load-end displacement curves for the composite shell associated with the first iteration (initial guess) and the final iteration (optimal solution). Again, as the solution converges from the initial guess to the optimal solution not only the critical buckling pressure of the shell is increased but also the postbuckling strength of the shell is greatly improved. Under the initial guess condition, there is a significant reduction on the critical buckling pressure and the postbuckling strength of the composite shell using the nonlinear shear formulation. However, under the optimal solution condition, the buckling and the postbuckling behaviors of the composite shell using the nonlinear shear formulation are very similar to those of the shell using the linear shear formulation.

Figure 8 shows the load-end displacement curves under optimal fiber angle conditions for the composite shells with $[\pm\theta/90_2/0]_s$ and $[\pm\phi/90_2/0_2/90_2/\mp\theta]$ laminate layups. It can be seen that under optimal fiber angle conditions (no matter what kinds of shear formulations are used) the buckling and the postbuckling strengths of the composite shell with the unsymmetric laminate layup are significantly higher than those of the shell with the symmetric laminate layup.

7. CONCLUSIONS

From the optimization results obtained in this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. For the optimization of simply supported composite shells subjected to external hydrostatic compression with $[\pm\theta/90_2/0]_s$ and $[\pm\phi/90_2/0_2/90_2/\mp\theta]$ laminate layups, the optimal fiber angles θ and ϕ obtained by using the nonlinear in-plane shear formulation are very close to those obtained by using the linear in-plane shear formulation.
2. For simply supported composite shells with $[\pm\theta/90_2/0]_s$ and $[\pm\phi/90_2/0_2/90_2/\mp\theta]$ laminate layups, under optimal fiber angle conditions the buckling and the postbuckling behaviors of the composite

shell using the nonlinear shear formulation are very similar to those of the shell using the linear shear formulation. However, under certain fiber angle conditions, the buckling and the postbuckling strengths of the composite shell using the nonlinear in-plane shear formulation may be significantly lower than those of the shell using the linear in-plane shear formulation.

3. Under optimal fiber angle conditions (no matter what kinds of shear formulations are used) the buckling and the postbuckling strengths of the composite shell with the unsymmetric laminate layup $[\pm\phi/90_2/0_2/90_2/\mp\theta]$ are significantly higher than those of the shell with the symmetric laminate layup $[\pm\theta/90_2/0]_s$.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work reported in this paper was supported by the Office of Naval Research through the University Research Initiative Program (Grant N00014-86-K-0799) to the National Center for Composite Materials Research at the University of Illinois.

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Fig. 1 Material and element coordinate systems for fiber composite laminate

Laminate layup:
 $[\pm\theta/90_2/0]_S$

Composite shell geometry:
 $L = 20.32 \text{ cm}$
 $D = 20.32 \text{ cm}$
 $t = 1.27 \text{ cm}$

Ply constitutive properties:
 $E_{11} = 138 \text{ Gpa}$
 $E_{22} = 14.5 \text{ Gpa}$
 $G_{12} = G_{13} = 5.86 \text{ Gpa}$
 $G_{23} = 3.52 \text{ Gpa}$
 $\nu_{12} = 0.21$
 $S_{6666} = 7.32 \text{ (Gpa)}^{-3}$

Fig. 2 Cylindrical fiber-composite laminate shell under external hydrostatic compression

Fig. 3 In-plane shear stress-strain curves for graphite/epoxy composite lamina

(a) Number of iterations N vs. fiber angle θ

(b) Number of iterations N vs. critical pressure p_{cr}

Fig. 4 Buckling optimization of simply supported $[\pm\theta/90_2/0]_S$ composite shell under hydrostatic compression, (a) number of iterations N vs. fiber angle θ , and (b) number of iterations N vs. critical pressure p_{cr}

Fig. 5 Load-end displacement curves for simply supported $[\pm\theta/90_2/0]_S$ composite shell under hydrostatic compression

Fig. 7 Load-end displacement curves for simply supported $[\pm\phi/90_2/0_2/90_2/\mp\theta]$ composite shell under hydrostatic compression

(a) Number of iterations N vs. fiber angles ϕ and θ

(b) Number of iterations N vs. critical pressure p_{cr}

Fig. 6 Buckling optimization of simply supported $[\pm\phi/90_2/0_2/90_2/\mp\theta]$ composite shell under hydrostatic compression, (a) number of iterations N vs. fiber angles ϕ and θ , and (b) number of iterations N vs. critical pressure p_{cr}

(a) with nonlinear shear formulation

(b) with linear shear formulation

Fig. 8 Load-end displacement curves under optimal fiber angle conditions for simply supported composite shells under hydrostatic compression with symmetric layup $[\pm\theta/90_2/0]_S$ and with unsymmetric layup $[\pm\phi/90_2/0_2/90_2/\mp\theta]$